

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF MODAL VERBS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES: TRANSFER AND TRANSLATION

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Abstract. This article gives information about linguistic features of modal verbs in English and Uzbek languages. It studies the transfer of modality and translation methods of English modal verbs into Uzbek language.

Key words: modality, transfer, translation, can, must, might, will, shall, obligation, possibility, ability.

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ МОДАЛЬНЫХ ГЛАГОЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ: ПЕРЕДАЧА И ПЕРЕВОД

Аннотация. В статье дана информация о лингвистических особенностях модальных глаголов в английском и узбекском языках. Изучает перенос модальности и способы перевода английских модальных глаголов на узбекский язык.

Ключевые слова: модальность, перевод, может, должен, может, воля, должен, обязанность, возможность, способность.

INTRODUCTION

Perhaps there is no other lexico-grammatical category in the English language that would present more difficulties in the translation process than the category of modality, it is a broad category that expresses the speaker's attitude to reality. It can be expressed primarily by mood forms, modal verbs and their equivalents and modal words. Modality plays a very important role in language. Modality is a grammatical category that reflects the speaker's attitude to the content of the utterance and the utterance itself to reality. This subjective attitude can be expressed by various means, words and phraseological units, mood, word order and even intonation. In the English language, modal verbs are allocated to a special group, characterized by the presence of features that belong only to verbs with modal meaning.

Modal verbs reflect many shades of meaning, namely: possibility and impossibility, necessity and obligation, probability, doubt, certainty, desirability, permission and prohibition". Therefore, if a translator ignores modal meanings and their shades, he thereby impoverishes the translation, deprives it of its emotional coloring, and in the worst case, simply distorts the meaning". Since modal verbs are described in detail in grammar textbooks, let's try to look through some cases of using modal verbs that may be interesting for a novice translator.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

The modal verb **must**, in addition to the *obligation*, can express an *assumption bordering on reality*. In these cases, it is translated as it should be. For example,

- *You must learn English* (obligation) – *Sen ingliz tini o'rganishing zarur* (zaruriyat, majburiyat)

- *That must be dangerous.* (assumption bordering on reality) - *Bu xavfli bo'lsa kerak.* (haqiqatga yaqin bo'lgan tahminiy fikr)
- *He must have got cold or else he definitely would come to the party.* (assumption bordering on reality) - *U shamollab qolgan bo'lsa kerak, aks holda bazmga albatta kelgan bo'lardi.* (haqiqatga yaqin bo'lgan tahminiy fikr)

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modal verbs **can/could**, when used in interrogative sentences, express *doubt* and *uncertainty*, acquiring an emotional connotation. In this case, these modal verbs are translated into Uzbek like *bo'lishi mumkinmi*, *chindan ham*, *nahotki*. For example,

- *Could this old woman be her aunt?* – *Bu keksa ayol chindan ham Madinami?* (Nahotki shu keksa ayol uning xolasi bo'lsa?)
- *She could not have changed like that.* - *U bu darajada o'zgargan bo'lishi mumkin emas.* (Chindan ham u shu qadar o'zgargan bo'lishi mumkin emas).

The verb *can*, when negated can express improbability and be translated as it cannot be (*bo'lishi mumkin emas*).

The modal verb **might** in combination with a perfect infinitive means action on the verge of accomplishment and is translated as “*sal qoldi*”. For example:

- *Watch your step! Yesterday I might have broken my leg here.* - *Ehtiyot bo'ling! Sal qoldi kecha bu yerda oyog'imni sindirib olardim.*

In addition to its main meanings - *probability*, *assumption* and *resolution*, the verb *might* is capable of expressing the idea of *similarity*.

In official documents, the modal verb **shall** can express a **must**:

- *Candidates shall return to their seats until all the papers have been collected.* - *Barcha hujjatlar yig'ilguncha nomzodlar o'z o'rinlariga qaytishlari kerak.*

The modal verb “**will**” combined with the infinitive means a *repetitive, habitual action*:

- *All nurses will always think that I'd like a nice cup of tea at 5 in the morning.* - *Odatda hamma hamshiralalar meni ertalab soat 5 da bir piyola choy xoxlaydi deb o'ylashadi.*

The modality form does not present much difficulty in translation, since there are similar forms in the Uzbek language. Uzbek modal particles (*axir*, *hech bo'lmaganda*, *aqalli*) are absent in the English language and can be expressed by other means.

- *After us the deluge.* – *Menda desa bizdan keyin dunyoni suv bosmaydimi?!*

CONCLUSION

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that modal phraseological units are characterized by modal types phraseological meaning: integral modal meaning; separating integral modal meaning, holistic communicative modal meaning, dividing integral communicative comparative meaning. As a result, speaking about the transfer of modality in translation, some features of the translation of English modal verbs and phrasal units were indicated in order to expand the students' general understanding of modality.

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